

Stability and out-of-sample validation of an empirical correction to Wolf’s formula for consecutive prime gaps

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Abstract

This is a short companion to [1]. The earlier paper proposed a two-parameter empirical correction

$$R(g, N) := \log(N_g^{\text{emp}}(N)/W(g, N)) \approx a \sqrt{\omega(g)} - b \log \log N$$

to Wolf’s heuristic $W(g, N) = C_g \cdot \text{Li}_2(N) \cdot \exp(-gC_g/\ln N)$ on a dataset of $n = 140$ points covering $N \in [10^5, 10^{13}]$, with no free intercept. We extend the dataset to $N \leq 3 \cdot 10^{14}$ (28 values of N , $n = 169$ on the primary filter $\rho \in [0.05, 1.10]$), adding three new N -values that were never seen during model selection in [1]. Three findings: (i) the model trained on $N \leq 10^{13}$ predicts the 29 new (g, N) points with weighted out-of-sample $R^2 = 0.986$, mean residual -0.005 and RMS 0.108 ; (ii) refitting on the full extended dataset yields $(a, b) = (0.836, -0.195)$, with $|a|$ and $|b|$ drifting by 2.2% and 3.5% from the baseline $(0.855, -0.202)$ and remaining inside the pre-extension block-bootstrap 95% intervals; (iii) the relaxed filter ($\rho \leq 4$) gains four new $\omega(g) = 3$ points in the extended range, including (at $N = 3 \cdot 10^{14}$) the first $\omega = 3$ point with $g \neq 30$: $g = 42$ ($\rho_{42} \approx 3.99$, $N_{42}^{\text{emp}} \approx 2.67 \cdot 10^{11}$). In v1 the entire $\omega = 3$ stratum was confined to $g = 30$. The intercept remains statistically unjustified (LR $p = 0.18$, $\Delta\text{BIC} = -3.30$) and the alt-form rejection of $\log C_g$ ($\Delta\text{AIC} = 52.6$) and $\sigma_0(g)$ ($\Delta\text{AIC} \geq 119.9$) is preserved. The functional form $\phi(\omega)$ remains under-determined on the primary support; one $\omega = 3$ point is enough to be a non-degenerate observation but not enough to discriminate among monotonic candidates.

1 Introduction

The earlier paper [1] (henceforth “v1”) proposed a two-parameter linear correction to the residual of Wolf’s 1998 heuristic [2] for the count of consecutive prime gaps, fitted on $n = 140$ points covering $N \in [10^5, 10^{13}]$. The headline form, M_1^* ,

$$\hat{y}(g, N) = \log(C_g \cdot \text{Li}_2(N)) - \frac{gC_g}{\ln N} + a \sqrt{\omega(g)} - b \log \log N, \quad (1)$$

has no free intercept, yielded $(a, b) = (0.855, -0.202)$, weighted loss $L = 1.111$, and median hold-out-one- N cross-validation $R_{\text{CV}}^2 = 0.92$ with a plateau at $R^2 \approx 0.94$ for $N \gtrsim 10^9$.

Section 6.7 of [1] flagged the cleanest fix to that work as “replication on a disjoint range – ideally $N \geq 10^{13}$ ”. We have now done the run. This note reports the resulting tests; we use the notation, definitions, filter ($\rho := gC_g/\ln N \in [0.05, 1.10]$, even $g \in [2, 100]$, $N_g^{\text{emp}} \geq 100$), and weighting ($w = \min(1, N_g^{\text{emp}}/1000)$) of v1 throughout, and refer the reader to v1 for motivation, sanity checks of the pipeline, the model-comparison framework $(M_0, M_1, M_1^*, M_2, M_3, M_4)$, and the literature context. For self-containment we recall only that C_g is the singular series (Hardy–Littlewood constant) for prime pairs at distance g , $\text{Li}_2(N) = \int_2^N dt/(\ln t)^2$, $N_g^{\text{emp}}(N)$ is the count of consecutive prime gaps of length exactly g below N , and $\omega(g)$ is the number of distinct prime divisors of g (so $\omega(2) = \omega(4) = 1$, $\omega(6) = \omega(10) = 2$, $\omega(30) = \omega(42) = 3$).

In memoriam. Marek Wolf, whose 1998 conjecture [2] is the object studied in v1 and here, passed away on 24 April 2026.

2 Data extension

Three sieve runs were performed for $N \in \{3 \cdot 10^{13}, 10^{14}, 3 \cdot 10^{14}\}$ on a single workstation, three single-threaded `primesieve`-based jobs running concurrently on separate cores. Total wall-clock time was 24 h 40 min, dominated by the largest run ($N = 3 \cdot 10^{14}$, 24 h 40 min on its own core). The histograms produced are bit-identical with the recipe of v1; sanity checks against Wolf, conducted exactly as in v1 §3.1, leave the residual structure of v1 intact: the empirical-to-Wolf ratio $N_g^{\text{emp}}(N)/W(g, N)$ on the new N values lies in $[0.97, 0.99]$ for $g \in \{2, 4, \dots, 16\}$, replicating the systematic underprediction visible at smaller N .

Three new record gaps appear in the extended range: $g = 766$ at $p = 19,581,334,192,423$ (merit 25.0, $N \leq 3 \cdot 10^{13}$), $g = 804$ at $p = 90,874,329,411,493$ (merit 25.0, $N \leq 10^{14}$), and $g = 906$ at $p = 218,209,405,436,543$ (merit 27.4, $N \leq 3 \cdot 10^{14}$). They sit in the relaxed-filter band ($g \gg \ln N$) where Wolf’s exponential collapses; they do not enter the primary fit but are recorded here for completeness.

After applying the primary filter the extended dataset has $n = 169$ on 28 values of N , of which 29 points come from the three new N values: 9 gaps at $N = 3 \cdot 10^{13}$, 10 at $N = 10^{14}$, and 10 at $N = 3 \cdot 10^{14}$, the per- N count growing slowly as larger g shrink below the ρ_{max} bound. The new points populate the same ω -stratification as the rest of the primary-filtered set ($\omega(g) \in \{1, 2\}$); $\omega = 3$ does not appear under the primary filter at any N in the dataset (§5 below).

3 Out-of-sample test

The training set is the primary-filtered v1 dataset ($n = 140$, $N \leq 10^{13}$); the test set is the 29 new points at $N \in \{3 \cdot 10^{13}, 10^{14}, 3 \cdot 10^{14}\}$. The fitted (a, b) from v1, used as a frozen predictor without any refit, gives on the test set

$$R_w^2(\text{test}) = 0.986, \quad \bar{r}_{\text{test}} = -0.005, \quad \text{RMS}(r_{\text{test}}) = 0.108.$$

The mean residual is statistically indistinguishable from zero, and the R^2 on a fully disjoint range exceeds the in-distribution cross-validation plateau of v1 (≈ 0.94 , see [1] Fig. 10). The three new N values lie a factor of 30 beyond the largest training N , so the test extrapolates over a non-trivial range.

This is direct evidence that the v1 fit is not an artefact of in-sample tuning: the same two coefficients describe data the model never saw at selection time. The qualifier is that $n_{\text{test}} = 29$ is modest, and the histograms at the three new N values are nested in the same way the v1 histograms are, so the effective sample size is closer to 3 than to 29. The result is a confirmation, not a discriminating test among the candidate models of v1, and does not bear on the M_1^* vs. M_3 ranking discussed in [1] §5.4.

4 Coefficient stability

Refitting M_1^* on the extended dataset gives

$$(a, b) = (0.836, -0.195), \tag{2}$$

to be compared with the v1 baseline $(0.855, -0.202)$: drifts of -2.2% in a and $+3.5\%$ in b . Both new values lie well inside the pre-extension block-bootstrap 5%/95% intervals reported in [1] §6.5: $a \in [0.791, 0.933]$, $b \in [-0.230, -0.179]$.

Figure 1: Out-of-sample residuals $\log N_g^{\text{emp}} - \hat{y}_{M_1^*}$ on the extended dataset, with M_1^* coefficients frozen at the v1 baseline $(a, b) = (0.855, -0.202)$. Blue dots are the $n = 140$ training points covering $N \leq 10^{13}$; red crosses are the $n_{\text{test}} = 29$ disjoint test points at $N \in \{3 \cdot 10^{13}, 10^{14}, 3 \cdot 10^{14}\}$. Left: residuals against the Wolf exponent $\rho = g C_g / \ln N$. Right: residuals against $\log \log N$. Test points trace the same family of curves as the training points and concentrate around zero on average.

Recomputed on the extended dataset, the block-bootstrap intervals (resampling 28 N -blocks with replacement, $B = 1000$) are

$$a \in [0.778, 0.906], \quad b \in [-0.220, -0.175],$$

narrowing the v1 5%/95% widths by about 10% on a (v1 width 0.142, post-B 0.128) and 12% on b (v1 width 0.051, post-B 0.045). The narrowing is modest given that n grew by 21%, because the across- N -block dependence dominates over the point count.

The intercept-removal test, repeated on $n = 169$, gives the same qualitative answer as v1: $\Delta \text{BIC}(M_1^* - M_1) = -3.30$ in favour of no intercept, $\chi_1^2(\text{LR}) = 1.83$, $p = 0.176$. Read together: the likelihood-ratio test does not reject the no-intercept restriction (improvement in fit consistent with one extra free parameter under the null), and the BIC penalises the intercept enough to put the posterior odds in favour of M_1^* ; both criteria therefore disfavour adding the intercept, which is the v1 reading. The Bayes-factor evidence is “positive” on the Kass–Raftery scale [3].

The alt-form scan from [1] §4.2, repeated on $n = 169$, shows the same pattern: the five monotonic transforms of $\omega(g)$ (top block of Tab. 1) collapse into a single AIC value because $\omega(g) \in \{1, 2\}$ on the primary filter; the three features that break this bijection ($\log C_g$, $\sqrt{\sigma_0(g)}$, $\sigma_0(g)$) lose by $\Delta \text{AIC} \in [52.6, 124.7]$, in each case slightly increased over the v1 values ($[47.4, 124.4]$).

5 First $\omega(g) = 3$ observation in the relaxed filter

Section 6.4 of [1] listed as a limitation that $\omega(g)$ takes only two values on the primary filter, so the functional form $\phi(\omega)$ is not pinned down. The relaxed filter ($\rho_{\text{max}} = 4$, outside Wolf’s regime of validity) admitted $\omega = 3$ already in v1, but only along a single g -slice: $g = 30$ ($C_{30} \approx 3.52$) at $N \in \{3 \cdot 10^{11}, 10^{12}, 3 \cdot 10^{12}, 10^{13}\}$, four points in total.

The B-run adds four further $\omega(g) = 3$ points to the relaxed filter:

- $g = 30$ at $N \in \{3 \cdot 10^{13}, 10^{14}, 3 \cdot 10^{14}\}$, three more points along the existing slice, with ρ_{30} decreasing from 3.40 to 3.17;
- $g = 42$ ($C_{42} \approx 3.17$) at $N = 3 \cdot 10^{14}$, where $\rho_{42} = 42 C_{42} / \ln(3 \cdot 10^{14}) \approx 3.99$ clears the $\rho_{\text{max}} = 4$ cut for the first time across all 28 values of N in the dataset; the empirical count

Table 1: Alternative features for the ω -dependent term, refit on $n = 169$ ($N \leq 3 \cdot 10^{14}$, primary filter $\rho \in [0.05, 1.10]$). Top block: monotonic transforms of $\omega(g)$, identical fits because $\omega \in \{1, 2\}$ remains binary on the extended dataset (§5); bottom block: features that break the two-value bijection, all rejected.

Feature	a	b	AIC	Δ AIC
$\sqrt{\omega(g)}$	+0.8239	-0.2255	-318.70	0.0
$\omega(g)$	+0.3413	-0.2255	-318.70	0.0
$\log \omega(g)$	+0.4923	-0.2255	-318.70	0.0
$\omega(g) - 1$	+0.3413	-0.2255	-318.70	0.0
$\sqrt{\omega(g) - 1}$	+0.3413	-0.2255	-318.70	0.0
$\log C_g$	+0.6124	-0.1507	-266.12	52.6
$\sqrt{\sigma_0(g)}$	+0.5195	-0.2126	-198.80	119.9
$\sigma_0(g)$	+0.1398	-0.2174	-194.00	124.7

is

$$N_{42}^{\text{emp}}(3 \cdot 10^{14}) = 267,266,372,230.$$

The qualitatively new feature is the second g -value at $\omega = 3$: until now the $\omega = 3$ stratum collapsed onto $g = 30$, with no within-stratum variation in g or in C_g . With $g \in \{30, 42\}$ a C_g -magnitude effect within the $\omega = 3$ stratum becomes (in principle) testable.

In practice two g -values at $\omega = 3$ reproduce the $\omega \in \{1, 2\}$ degeneracy at the next level: any monotonic transform of ω still fits, and discriminating between $\sqrt{\omega}$, ω , $\log \omega$, $\omega - 1$, $\sqrt{\omega - 1}$ at $\omega = 3$ remains under-determined. The next $\omega = 3$ candidate by ascending $g C_g$ product is $g = 70 = 2 \cdot 5 \cdot 7$ ($C_{70} \approx 2.11$, $g C_g \approx 148$), which would enter the relaxed filter only at $N \gtrsim 10^{16}$. Closing the gap between the two regimes is left for future work.

6 Discussion

What this paper does and does not show. The three results above (out-of-sample R^2 , coefficient stability, first $\omega = 3$ point) do not change the qualitative reading of v1: M_1^* is the minimally parametrised descriptor, the coefficients have no analytical derivation, and the M_3 vs. M_1^* ranking on AIC remains $\Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{eff}} \approx -21$ in favour of M_3 on $n = 169$ ($n_{\text{eff}} \approx 28$, nominal $\Delta\text{AIC} = -127.4$, rescale factor $28/169 \approx 0.166$; an analogous calculation to §5.4 of v1 where the rescale factor was $25/140 \approx 0.179$). The case for M_1^* over a reparametrised Wolf is therefore unchanged from v1, modulo the new bootstrap intervals quoted in §4.

What changes is the empirical confidence in the v1 claim itself. In v1 the strongest defence against the objection that the model had been fit to the same data on which it was selected was the leave-one- N -out cross-validation, which inevitably re-uses points within each fold. The disjoint test in §3 above is stronger: the held-out points come from N values that did not exist in the training data and that the model was not aware of at selection time. The result $R^2 = 0.986$ with mean residual ≈ 0 on those points is the direct out-of-sample confirmation v1 §6.7 asked for.

What the data still cannot decide. The functional form $\phi(\omega)$ remains under-determined. The primary filter still has $\omega \in \{1, 2\}$, the relaxed filter now has one $\omega = 3$ point, and any monotonic candidate still fits both. Pinning ϕ down would need either a substantially wider ω -range (which the filter geometry admits only in the relaxed band, where Wolf’s exponential mispredicts by orders of magnitude and the residual being modelled there is dominated by raw misprediction rather than a subleading correction) or a theoretical argument; this paper supplies

neither. The independent-line-of-evidence that the gap sequence violates the Cramér null at $\rho(1) \approx -0.03$ (v1 §5.5) extends qualitatively to longer-range structure – a separate paper in preparation reports the autocorrelation profile $\rho(k)$ over $N \in [10^8, 10^{12}]$ – but does not transfer to a discriminating test among ω -features on $\{1, 2, 3\}$.

Effective sample size. The 169 points are not statistically independent: at each fixed N the histogram counts $\{N_g^{\text{emp}}(N)\}_g$ are drawn from one realisation of the prime sequence, so we treat each N -block as one effective draw and set n_{eff} equal to the number of distinct N -values (28 here, 25 in v1). This is the same convention used in [1] §5.4 to rescale the nominal $|\Delta\text{AIC}|$ values by the factor n_{eff}/n ($28/169 \approx 0.166$ here, $25/140 \approx 0.179$ in v1). The qualitative ranking is the same as in v1: $M_3 \succ M_1^* \succ M_2$ on rescaled criteria, with $M_1^* \succ M_2$ below the Burnham–Anderson threshold of 10 and $M_3 \succ M_1^*$ above it but no longer in the decisive band of Burnham–Anderson.

Open directions. (i) An $N \geq 10^{15}$ run would put $g = 30$ ($\rho_{30}(10^{15}) \approx 3.06$) inside the relaxed filter and add several $\omega = 3$ points; the wall-time scaling observed here ($N = 10^{14} \rightarrow 7 \text{ h } 56 \text{ min}$, $N = 3 \cdot 10^{14} \rightarrow 24 \text{ h } 40 \text{ min}$ on a single core) projects $N = 10^{15}$ to roughly 80 h single-thread. (ii) A theoretical derivation of the $a \cdot \sqrt{\omega} - b \cdot \log \log N$ form (equivalently of the ω -dependence of the residual to Wolf’s exponential) remains the natural follow-up; the heuristic of [1] §6.1 motivates the leading ω -dependence but neither the functional form nor the magnitude of b . (iii) The autocorrelation work mentioned above is treated separately; it concerns a different object (the gap sequence rather than the marginal histogram counts) and a different statistical framework.

Acknowledgements

This work extends the formula proposed by Marek Wolf (1949–2026) in his 1998 work [2]; we are grateful for the lasting impact of that contribution.

Reproducibility

The code, data, and notebooks underlying both v1 and this companion are available at <https://github.com/dkrse/math-02-wolf>; the extended dataset and the analysis notebooks 09–12 used here are end-to-end reproducible from `run_extension/post_launch.sh`. Dependency versions are pinned in `requirements.txt`. The three new sieve outputs and their SHA-256 sums are in `ml_data/` of the repository.

References

- [1] Sestak, K. (2026). An empirical subleading correction to Wolf’s formula for consecutive prime gaps. Preprint, version 1. doi:10.5281/zenodo.19796305.
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